

Single Mass Analysis

Tolerance = 5.0 PPM / DBE: min = -1.5, max = 100.0

Element prediction: Off

Number of isotope peaks used for i-FIT = 9

Monoisotopic Mass, Even Electron Ions

100 formula(e) evaluated with 1 results within limits (up to 50 closest results for each mass)

Elements Used:

C: 0-80 H: 0-100 N: 5-7 O: 7-9 Br: 1-1 P: 0-1

Order# 3081 Matthew Egleston ME385
 Synapt_32641a 18 (0.440) Cm (17:18-5:8)

SCS, UIUC

SYNAPT G2-Si#UGA305
 1: TOF MS ES+
 3.71e+005

Minimum: -1.5
 Maximum: 5.0 5.0 100.0

Mass	Calc. Mass	mDa	PPM	DBE	i-FIT	Norm	Conf (%)	Formula
663.0960	663.0968	-0.8	-1.2	15.5	423.9	n/a	n/a	C26 H29 N6 O8 Br P